

DYNAMICAL STUDY OF A STOCHASTIC SICR EPIDEMIC MODEL

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Abstract

In this paper, a stochastic SICR epidemic model is investigated. At first, we prove that the system exists a unique global positive solution. Then by means of the method of constructing appropriate Lyapunov functions which are given in the condition that the model is affected by environment fluctuations, we deduce sufficient conditions for the ergodic stationary distribution of the stochastic model. In addition, sufficient conditions for the extinction and persistence of the disease are established. In the end, numerical simulations are implemented to support our analytical results.

Keywords Stochastic SICR model, Stationary distribution, Extinction, Persistence, Numerical simulation

1. Introduction

Community attach great importance to the infectious diseases caused by viral infections all over the world. We will be more likely to involve our mind or body to better study virus infections incorporating Hepatitis B virus (HBV) infection in a plenty of different viral infectious diseases. The forms of expression for virus infections will be divided into a number of categories that include acute, deadly fulminant infection, as well as chronic infection for example Chronic Hepatitis B (CHB), which can result in a host of serious complications such as horrible cancer. The reason why we pay great attention to HBV virus infection is that the general population have a high virus carrier rate. In fact, the infection of the liver cells leads to HBV infection which is a widely prevalent hepatological problem. [1].

In order to do some research of population dynamics, epidemiology, and viral dynamics as well as other biological practical problems, it is usually better to resort to mathematical models that have become a crucial tool in the respects of these problem. For instance, Song and Neumann came up with a system that has the saturated infection rate to investigate viral infection dynamics (see [2]). Li, Wang, Yang study dynamical behaviors of a hepatitis B virus (HBV) infection model with logistic hepatocyte growth in [3] and so on. In the base of the ideas presented in the literature [4], For the first time Qiao, Liu and Forsys design the epidemic model of SICR in order to better investigate the dynamics of the virus infection in [5]. The SICR model is as follows

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dS(t)}{dt} = \mu - \beta S(t)I(t) - \alpha \beta S(t)C(t) - \mu S(t), \\ \frac{dI(t)}{dt} = \beta S(t)I(t) + \alpha \beta S(t)C(t) - \gamma_1 I(t) - \mu I(t), \\ \frac{dC(t)}{dt} = q\gamma_1 I(t) - \gamma_2 C(t) - \mu C(t), \\ \frac{dR(t)}{dt} = (1-q)\gamma_1 I(t) + \gamma_2 C(t) - \mu R(t), \end{cases} \quad (1.1)$$

where $S(t)$, $I(t)$, $C(t)$, $R(t)$ represent a group of susceptible people being not prior to exposed to the pathogen, the acutely infectious people being invaded by the pathogen at present and showing symptoms of the infection, the people carrying the viruses, the recovered people being successful in getting rid of the viral infection, respectively. In addition, the meaning of each parameter is shown as follows

- μ stands for the recruitment rate and the natural death rate of people;
- γ_1 demotes the rate of getting rid of the acutely infectious group;
- γ_2 means the rate of going away from virus carrier group for people;
- β shows the contacts rate between susceptible people and infectious or carriers people;

· $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ expresses the increased transmission rate from acute infectious people compared with viral carriers;

· $q \in [0, 1]$ is the ratio of those who are turned into the recovered people.

These parameters all are positive constant above.

For the reason that the fourth equation of system (1.1) is uncoupled, we can reduce (1.1) to the following subsystem

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dS(t)}{dt} = \mu - \beta S(t)I(t) - \alpha\beta S(t)C(t) - \mu S(t), \\ \frac{dI(t)}{dt} = \beta S(t)I(t) + \alpha\beta S(t)C(t) - \gamma_1 I(t) - \mu I(t), \\ \frac{dC(t)}{dt} = q\gamma_1 I(t) - \gamma_2 C(t) - \mu C(t), \end{cases} \quad (1.2)$$

The initial condition of system (1.2) is $(S(0), I(0), C(0)) \in \mathbb{R}_+^3$.

According to the theory in [5], system (1.2) has the following properties:

$\Gamma = \{(S(t), I(t), C(t)) \in \mathbb{R}_+^3 : S(t) + I(t) + C(t) \leq 1\}$ is positively invariant for (1.2).

The disease free equilibrium $E_0 = (S_0, I_0, C_0) = (1, 0, 0)$, which always exists, is globally asymptotically

stable if $R_0 = \frac{\beta}{\gamma_1 + \mu} + \frac{q\gamma_1}{\gamma_1 + \mu} \frac{\alpha\beta}{\gamma_2 + \mu} \leq 1$.

When $R_0 > 1$, system (1.2) has a unique positive equilibrium E^* and it is globally asymptotically stable.

However, in the real world, it is inevitable for the biological-mathematic models to be affected by environmental noise [6, 7, 8, 9]. Hence, in order to make a more accurate predict for the dynamics nature of the epidemics system, it is more reliable for us to use stochastic differential equations models. Owing to this reason, many authors choose to add stochastic perturbations into the deterministic models for the sake of better account for the influences of the environmental fluctuations. For instance, Zhang, Jiang, Hayat and Ahmad study the dynamical behavior of stochastic SVIR models in the literature [10]. Wang, Jiang, Alsaedi, Hayat investigate a stochastic HIV viral model with both logistic target cell growth and nonlinear immune response function and derive the conditions of the extinction of the disease. In addition, they also prove the existence of the ergodic stationary distribution (see [11]). With respect to the rest of literatures, one can also refer to [12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18].

Inspired by the above works, in this paper, we introduce stochastic perturbations into the model (1.2), we make the assumption that stochastic perturbations use the form of the white noise and they are directly proportional to $S(t), I(t), C(t)$ in system (1.2). Then the stochastic version corresponding to system (1.2) has the following form

$$\begin{cases} dS(t) = [\mu - \beta S(t)I(t) - \alpha\beta S(t)C(t) - \mu S(t)]dt + \sigma_1 S(t)dB_1(t), \\ dI(t) = [\beta S(t)I(t) + \alpha\beta S(t)C(t) - \gamma_1 I(t) - \mu I(t)]dt + \sigma_2 I(t)dB_2(t), \\ dC(t) = [q\gamma_1 I(t) - \gamma_2 C(t) - \mu C(t)]dt + \sigma_3 C(t)dB_3(t), \end{cases} \quad (1.3)$$

where $B_i(t), i = 1, 2, 3$, are the white noises, in other word, $B = (B_1(t), B_2(t), B_3(t), t \geq 0)$ is mutually independent standard Brownian motions defined on a complete probability space (Ω, F, P) with a filtration $\{F_t\}_{t \geq 0}$ satisfying the general conditions (i.e., it is increasing and right continuous while F_0 contains all P -null sets), $\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3$ stands for the intensities of the white noise and $\sigma_i > 0 (i = 1, 2, 3)$. All the other parameters have the same meaning as that of the system (1.2).

This paper is organized as following: In the next section, we verify that there exists a unique global positive solution of system (1.3) for any initial value. In Section 3, we will prove the existence of the ergodic stationary distribution of the stochastic model. In section 4, we obtain the conditions of the extinction and persistence for stochastic system (1.3). Finally, the numerical simulations are put into force in Section 5 to verify the main theoretical results. A brief discussion is given in last part to conclude this work.

2 Existence and uniqueness of the global positive solution

In this section, It is deduced that the solution of system (1.3) is global and positive for any initial value. As everyone knows, if we want to prove that a stochastic differential equation have a unique global solution (i.e., no explosion at any finite time) to the system (1.3) for any initial value, in a general way, the coefficients of the system

have to satisfy the linear growth condition and local Lipschitz condition (see [19]). However, though the coefficients of system (1.3) are locally Lipschitz continuous, they do not satisfy the linear growth condition, hence the solution of system (1.3) may explode at a finite time. In the following, we will prove that there is a unique global positive solution of system (1.3) for any initial value.

Theorem 2.1 For any initial value $(S(0), I(0), C(0)) \in R_+^3$, there is a unique positive solution $(S(t), I(t), C(t))$ on $t \geq 0$ for system (1.3), further, the solution will remain in R_+^3 with probability one, in brief, $(S(t), I(t), C(t)) \in R_+^3$ for all $t \geq 0$ almost surely (a.s).

Proof. Since the coefficients of system (1.3) satisfy locally Lipschitz condition, so system (1.3) for any initial value exists a unique local solution $(S(t), I(t), C(t))$ on $t \in [0, \tau_e)$, where τ_e is the explosion time [20]. Next for the sake of illustrating this solution is global, it is significant for us to verify that $\tau_e = \infty$ a.s. At this time, let

$k_0 \geq 1$ be enough large such that $S(0), I(0), C(0)$ all lie within the interval $[\frac{1}{k_0}, k_0]$. For each integer $k \geq k_0$,

define the stopping time

$$\tau_k = \inf\{t \in [0, \tau_e) : S(t) \notin (\frac{1}{k}, k) \text{ or } I(t) \notin (\frac{1}{k}, k) \text{ or } C(t) \notin (\frac{1}{k}, k)\},$$

where throughout this paper, we set $\inf \emptyset = \infty$ (as usual $\emptyset$ is the empty set). Clearly τ_k is increasing when $k \rightarrow \infty$. Let $\tau_\infty = \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \tau_k$, whence $\tau_\infty \leq \tau_e$ a.s. If we can show $\tau_\infty = \infty$, then $\tau_e = \infty$ and $(S(t), I(t), C(t)) \in R_+^3$ a.s. for all $t \geq 0$. That shows that we are requested to illustrate that $\tau_\infty = \infty$ a.s. in order to finish the proof. If this assertion is not true, then there is a pair of constants $T > 0$ and $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$ such that

$$P\{\tau_\infty \leq T\} > \varepsilon.$$

Hence there is an integer $k_1 \geq k_0$ such that for all $k \geq k_1$

$$P\{\tau_k \leq T\} \geq \varepsilon. \quad (2.1)$$

Define a C^2 — function $V : R_+^3 \rightarrow R_+$ by

$$V(S, I, C) = (S - b - b \ln \frac{S}{b}) + (I - 1 - \ln I) + fC.$$

where b, f are positive constants to be determined later. The nonnegativity of this function can be attained from $u - 1 - \ln u \geq 0$ for any $u > 0$. Using Itô formula to V , we get:

$$\begin{aligned} dV &= (1 - \frac{b}{S})dS + (1 - \frac{1}{I})dI + fdC + \frac{1}{2} \frac{b}{S^2} (dS)^2 + \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{I^2} (dI)^2 \\ &= (1 - \frac{b}{S})[(\mu - \beta SI - \alpha \beta SC - \mu S)dt + \sigma_1 S dB_1(t)] + \frac{1}{2} b \sigma_1^2 dt \\ &\quad + (1 - \frac{1}{I})[(\beta SI + \alpha \beta SC - \gamma_1 I - \mu I)dt + \sigma_2 I dB_2(t)] + \frac{1}{2} \sigma_2^2 dt \\ &\quad + f[(q\gamma_1 I - \gamma_2 C - \mu C)dt + \sigma_3 C dB_3(t)] \\ &= LVdt + \sigma_1(S - b)dB_1(t) + \sigma_2(I - 1)dB_2(t) + f\sigma_3 C dB_3(t). \end{aligned}$$

where LV is defined by

$$\begin{aligned}
LV &= (1 - \frac{b}{S})(\mu - \beta SI - \alpha\beta SC - \mu S) + \frac{1}{2}b\sigma_1^2 + (1 - \frac{1}{I})(\beta SI \\
&\quad + \alpha\beta SC - \gamma_1 I - \mu I) + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_2^2 + f(q\gamma_1 I - \gamma_2 C - \mu C) \\
&= (b+2)\mu - (\mu + \beta)S - \frac{b\mu}{S} - \frac{\alpha\beta SC}{I} + \gamma_1 + \frac{1}{2}b\sigma_1^2 + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_2^2 \\
&\quad + (b\beta + fq\gamma_1 - \gamma_1 - \mu)I + (b\alpha\beta - f\gamma_2 - f\mu)C \\
&\leq (b+2)\mu + \gamma_1 + \frac{1}{2}b\sigma_1^2 + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_2^2 + (b\beta + fq\gamma_1 - \gamma_1 - \mu)I + (b\alpha\beta - f\gamma_2 - f\mu)C.
\end{aligned}$$

We choose $b = \frac{(\gamma_1 + \mu)(\gamma_2 + \mu)}{\beta(\gamma_2 + \mu + \alpha q\gamma_1)}$ and $f = \frac{\alpha(\gamma_1 + \mu)}{\gamma_2 + \mu + \alpha q\gamma_1}$ such that $(b\beta + fq\gamma_1 - \gamma_1 - \mu)I = 0$ and $(b\alpha\beta - f\gamma_2 - f\mu)C = 0$, then we can attain

$$LV \leq (b+2)\mu + \gamma_1 + \frac{1}{2}b\sigma_1^2 + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_2^2 := K.$$

In which K is a positive constant. So we have:

$$dV \leq Kdt + \sigma_1(S-b)dB_1(t) + \sigma_2(I-1)dB_2(t) + f\sigma_3 CdB_3(t) \quad (2.2)$$

Integrating of (2.2) from 0 to $\tau_K \wedge T$ and then taking the expectation on both sides, further according to Theorem 1.5.8 (ii) [20], we can obtain:

$$EV(S(\tau_K \wedge T), I(\tau_K \wedge T), C(\tau_K \wedge T)) \leq V(S(0), I(0), C(0)) + KE(\tau_K \wedge T).$$

Therefore,

$$EV(S(\tau_K \wedge T), I(\tau_K \wedge T), C(\tau_K \wedge T)) \leq V(S(0), I(0), C(0)) + KT. \quad (2.3)$$

Set $\Omega_k = \{\tau_k \leq T\}$ for $k \geq k_1$ and by means of (2.1), we can obtain $P(\Omega_k) \geq \varepsilon$. Notice that for every $\omega \in \Omega_k$, there exists that $S(\tau_k, \omega)$ or $I(\tau_k, \omega)$ or $C(\tau_k, \omega)$ equals either k or $\frac{1}{k}$. Therefore,

$V(S(\tau_k, \omega), I(\tau_k, \omega), C(\tau_k, \omega))$ is no less than either $k - 1 - \ln k$ or $\frac{1}{k} - 1 + \ln k$.

Consequently, we have

$$V(S(\tau_k, \omega), I(\tau_k, \omega), C(\tau_k, \omega)) \geq (k - 1 - \ln k) \wedge (\frac{1}{k} - 1 + \ln k) := H(k).$$

According to (2.3), we can attain:

$$\begin{aligned}
V(S(0), I(0), C(0)) + KT &\geq E(I_{\Omega_k}(\omega)V(S(\tau_k \wedge T), I(\tau_k \wedge T), C(\tau_k \wedge T))) \\
&\geq P(\Omega_k(\omega))H(k) \\
&\geq \varepsilon H(k),
\end{aligned}$$

where I_{Ω_k} stands for the indicator function of Ω_k . Letting $k \rightarrow \infty$, then

$$\infty > V(S(0), I(0), C(0)) + KT \geq \varepsilon H(k) \rightarrow \infty,$$

which lead to the contradiction. Thus the proof is completed.

3 Existence of ergodic stationary distribution of system (1.3)

We pay great attention to when the disease will prevail in the population when we take into account epidemic model. The method of solving this problem for deterministic model is by means of the endemic equilibrium of the corresponding model, to be specific, we can prove that the endemic equilibrium of the system is globally asymptotically stable or is a global attractor. However, for the stochastic system (1.3), it does not have the endemic equilibrium. So in this section, we will derive the conditions of the existence of ergodic stationary distribution of system (1.3) according to the theory of Has'minskii [21]. In the following, we introduce some theories about stationary distributions, which is essential in the process of our proof(see [22]).

Assuming that $X(t)$ is a regular time-homogeneous Markov process in the d —dimensional space E_d , and satisfy the following stochastic equation

$$dX(t) = b(X)dt + \sum_{r=1}^k g_r(X)dB_r(t).$$

At this time, the diffusion matrix has the following form

$$A(X) = (a_{ij}(x)), a_{ij}(x) = \sum_{r=1}^k g_r^i(x)g_r^j(x).$$

Lemma 3.1(see [12])For Markov process $X(t)$, there is a unique ergodic stationary distribution $\pi(\cdot)$ if it exists a bounded domain $D \in E_d$ with regular boundary Γ and

(H1)there exists a constant $M > 0$ satisfying $\sum_{i,j=1}^d a_{ij}(x)\xi_i\xi_j \geq M|\xi|^2, x \in D, \xi \in R^d$.

(H2)there is a C^2 - function $V \geq 0$ such that LV is negative for any given $E_d \setminus D$. Then

$$P\{\limsup_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T f(X(t))dt = \int_{E_d} f(x)\pi(dx)\} = 1,$$

for all $x \in E_d$, where $f(\cdot)$ is an integrable function about the measure π .

Theorem 3.1 Assume that

$$R_0^S := \frac{\beta\mu}{(\mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_1^2)(\gamma_1 + \mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_2^2)} + \frac{\alpha\beta q\gamma_1\mu}{(\mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_1^2)(\gamma_1 + \mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_2^2)(\gamma_2 + \mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_3^2)} > 1,$$

then system (1.3) has a unique stationary distribution $\pi(\cdot)$ and the ergodicity holds.

Proof. In order to prove Theorem 3.1, we need to verify the conditions of Lemma 3.1. First, we will verify that the condition (H2) in Lemma 3.1 is valid.

Define

$$V_1 = -\ln I - (a_1 + b_1) \ln S - b_2 \ln C + \frac{\alpha\beta(a_1 + b_1)}{\gamma_2 + \mu} C,$$

$$V_2 = -\ln S - \ln C + \frac{\alpha\beta}{\gamma_2 + \mu} C,$$

$$V_3 = \frac{1}{\theta + 1} (S + I + C)^{\theta + 1},$$

where a_1, b_1, b_2 are positive constants to be determined later. $\theta \in (0, 1)$ satisfy

$$\mu - \frac{\theta}{2}(\sigma_1^2 \vee \sigma_2^2 \vee \sigma_3^2) > 0.$$

Applying the Itô formula, we can attain

$$\begin{aligned} LV_1 &= -\beta S - \frac{\alpha\beta SC}{I} + \gamma_1 + \mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_2^2 - \frac{a_1\mu}{S} - \frac{b_1\mu}{S} + \beta(a_1 + b_1)I + \frac{\alpha\beta q\gamma_1(a_1 + b_1)}{\gamma_2 + \mu} I \\ &\quad + \mu(a_1 + b_1) + \frac{1}{2}(a_1 + b_1)\sigma_1^2 - \frac{b_2 q\gamma_1 I}{C} + b_2\gamma_2 + b_2\mu + \frac{1}{2}b_2\sigma_3^2 \\ &= -\beta S - \frac{a_1\mu}{S} + a_1(\mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_1^2) - \frac{\alpha\beta SC}{I} - \frac{b_1\mu}{S} - \frac{b_2 q\gamma_1 I}{C} + b_1(\mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_1^2) \\ &\quad + b_2(\gamma_2 + \mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_3^2) + \gamma_1 + \mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_2^2 + \frac{\beta(a_1 + b_1)(\gamma_2 + \mu + \alpha q\gamma_1)}{\gamma_2 + \mu} I \\ &\leq -2\sqrt{\beta a_1\mu} + a_1(\mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_1^2) - 3\sqrt[3]{\alpha\beta q\gamma_1\mu b_1 b_2} + b_1(\mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_1^2) \\ &\quad + b_2(\gamma_2 + \mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_3^2) + \gamma_1 + \mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_2^2 + \frac{\beta(a_1 + b_1)(\gamma_2 + \mu + \alpha q\gamma_1)}{\gamma_2 + \mu} I. \end{aligned}$$

Let

$$a_1 = \frac{\beta\mu}{(\mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_1^2)^2}, b_1 = \frac{\alpha\beta q\gamma_1\mu}{(\mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_1^2)^2(\gamma_2 + \mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_3^2)}, b_2 = \frac{\alpha\beta q\gamma_1\mu}{(\mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_1^2)(\gamma_2 + \mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_3^2)^2}.$$

Then we have

$$\begin{aligned}
LV_1 &\leq -\frac{\beta\mu}{\mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_1^2} - \frac{\alpha\beta q\gamma_1\mu}{(\mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_1^2)(\gamma_2 + \mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_3^2)} + \gamma_1 + \mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_2^2 + \frac{\beta(a_1 + b_1)(\gamma_2 + \mu + \alpha q\gamma_1)}{\gamma_2 + \mu} I \\
&= -(\gamma_1 + \mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_2^2)(R_0^S - 1) + \frac{\beta(a_1 + b_1)(\gamma_2 + \mu + \alpha q\gamma_1)}{\gamma_2 + \mu} I \\
&=: -\lambda + \frac{\beta(a_1 + b_1)(\gamma_2 + \mu + \alpha q\gamma_1)}{\gamma_2 + \mu} I.
\end{aligned} \tag{3.1}$$

where

$$\lambda = (\gamma_1 + \mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_2^2)(R_0^S - 1) > 0.$$

Also, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
LV_2 &= -\frac{\mu}{S} - \frac{q\gamma_1 I}{C} + \frac{\beta(\gamma_2 + \mu + \alpha q\gamma_1)}{\gamma_2 + \mu} I + \gamma_2 + 2\mu + \frac{\sigma_1^2 + \sigma_3^2}{2}. \tag{3.2} \\
LV_3 &= (S + I + C)^0 [\mu - \mu(S + I + C) - (\gamma_1 - q\gamma_1)I - \gamma_2 C] \\
&\quad + \frac{\theta}{2} (S + I + C)^{\theta-1} (\sigma_1^2 S^2 + \sigma_2^2 I^2 + \sigma_3^2 C^2) \\
&\leq \mu(S + I + C)^0 - \mu(S + I + C)^{\theta+1} + \frac{\theta}{2} (S + I + C)^{\theta-1} (\sigma_1^2 S^2 + \sigma_2^2 I^2 + \sigma_3^2 C^2) \\
&\leq \mu(S + I + C)^0 - [\mu - \frac{\theta}{2} (\sigma_1^2 \vee \sigma_2^2 \vee \sigma_3^2)] (S + I + C)^{\theta+1} \\
&\leq B - \frac{1}{2} [\mu - \frac{\theta}{2} (\sigma_1^2 \vee \sigma_2^2 \vee \sigma_3^2)] (S + I + C)^{\theta+1} \\
&\leq B - \frac{1}{2} [\mu - \frac{\theta}{2} (\sigma_1^2 \vee \sigma_2^2 \vee \sigma_3^2)] (S^{\theta+1} + I^{\theta+1} + C^{\theta+1}),
\end{aligned} \tag{3.3}$$

where

$$B = \sup_{(S, I, C) \in \mathbb{R}_+^3} \{ \mu(S + I + C)^0 - \frac{1}{2} [\mu - \frac{\theta}{2} (\sigma_1^2 \vee \sigma_2^2 \vee \sigma_3^2)] (S + I + R)^{\theta+1} \} < \infty.$$

Defining a C^2 -function $\hat{V}(S, I, C) : \mathbb{R}_+^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ as follows

$$\hat{V}(S, I, C) = MV_1 + V_2 + V_3.$$

where M is positive constants to be determined later.

It is obvious to see that

$$\liminf_{k \rightarrow \infty, (S, I, C) \in \mathbb{R}_+^3 \setminus U_k} \hat{V}(S, I, C) = +\infty,$$

at which $U_k = (\frac{1}{k}, k) \times (\frac{1}{k}, k) \times (\frac{1}{k}, k)$. So, $\hat{V}(S, I, C)$ is a continuous function which processes a minimum point $(\bar{S}_0, \bar{I}_0, \bar{C}_0)$ in the interior of $\mathbb{R}_+^3$.

Therefore, we can define a non-negative C^2 -function $V(S, I, C) : \mathbb{R}_+^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ as follows

$$V(S, I, C) = \hat{V}(S, I, C) - \hat{V}(\bar{S}_0, \bar{I}_0, \bar{C}_0).$$

From (3.1), (3.2) and (3.3), we have that

$$\begin{aligned}
LV &\leq -M\lambda - \frac{\mu}{S} - \frac{q\gamma_1 I}{C} + \frac{\beta(\gamma_2 + \mu + \alpha q\gamma_1)(Ma_1 + Mb_1 + 1)}{\gamma_2 + \mu} I + \gamma_2 + 2\mu \\
&\quad + \frac{\sigma_1^2 + \sigma_3^2}{2} + B - \frac{1}{2} [\mu - \frac{\theta}{2} (\sigma_1^2 \vee \sigma_2^2 \vee \sigma_3^2)] (S^{\theta+1} + I^{\theta+1} + C^{\theta+1}) \\
&=: -M\lambda - \frac{\mu}{S} - \frac{q\gamma_1 I}{C} + \frac{\beta(\gamma_2 + \mu + \alpha q\gamma_1)(Ma_1 + Mb_1 + 1)}{\gamma_2 + \mu} I + Q(S, I, C),
\end{aligned}$$

where

$$Q(S, I, C) = \gamma_2 + 2\mu + \frac{\sigma_1^2 + \sigma_3^2}{2} + B - \frac{1}{2} \left[\mu - \frac{\theta}{2} (\sigma_1^2 \vee \sigma_2^2 \vee \sigma_3^2) \right] (S^{\theta+1} + I^{\theta+1} + C^{\theta+1}).$$

Let M is a positive constant and satisfy

$$-M\lambda + F \leq -2, \quad (3.4)$$

where

$$F = \sup_{(S, I, C) \in R_+^3} Q(S, I, C) < \infty.$$

Now, we define a bounded closed set as

$$D_\varepsilon = \left\{ (S, I, C) \in R_+^3 : \varepsilon \leq S \leq \frac{1}{\varepsilon}, \varepsilon \leq I \leq \frac{1}{\varepsilon}, \varepsilon^2 \leq C \leq \frac{1}{\varepsilon^2} \right\}.$$

at which $\varepsilon > 0$ is a sufficiently small positive constant according with the following inequalities

$$-\frac{\mu}{\varepsilon} + U \leq -1. \quad (3.5)$$

$$-M\lambda + \frac{\beta(\gamma_2 + \mu + \alpha q \gamma_1)(Ma_1 + Mb_1 + 1)}{\gamma_2 + \mu} \varepsilon + F \leq -1. \quad (3.6)$$

$$-\frac{q\gamma_1}{\varepsilon} + U \leq -1. \quad (3.7)$$

$$-\frac{1}{4} \left[\mu - \frac{\theta}{2} (\sigma_1^2 \vee \sigma_2^2 \vee \sigma_3^2) \right] \frac{1}{\varepsilon^{\theta+1}} + G \leq -1. \quad (3.8)$$

$$-\frac{1}{4} \left[\mu - \frac{\theta}{2} (\sigma_1^2 \vee \sigma_2^2 \vee \sigma_3^2) \right] \frac{1}{\varepsilon^{\theta+1}} + H \leq -1. \quad (3.9)$$

$$-\frac{1}{4} \left[\mu - \frac{\theta}{2} (\sigma_1^2 \vee \sigma_2^2 \vee \sigma_3^2) \right] \frac{1}{\varepsilon^{2(\theta+1)}} + N \leq -1. \quad (3.10)$$

where U, G, H, N are all positive constant according with the equations (3.12),(3.16),(3.18),(3.20). Therefore,

$R_+^3 \setminus D_\varepsilon$ can be divided into six domains

$$D_1 = \{(S, I, C) \in R_+^3, 0 < S < \varepsilon\}, D_2 = \{(S, I, C) \in R_+^3, 0 < I < \varepsilon\},$$

$$D_3 = \{(S, I, C) \in R_+^3, 0 < C < \varepsilon^2, I \geq \varepsilon\}, D_4 = \{(S, I, C) \in R_+^3, S > \frac{1}{\varepsilon}\},$$

$$D_5 = \{(S, I, C) \in R_+^3, I > \frac{1}{\varepsilon}\}, D_6 = \{(S, I, C) \in R_+^3, C > \frac{1}{\varepsilon^2}\}.$$

In the following we will illustrate $LV(S, I, C) \leq -1$ for any given $(S, I, C) \in R_+^3 \setminus D_\varepsilon$.

Case 1. If $(S, I, C) \in D_1$, then we have that

$$\begin{aligned} LV &\leq -M\lambda - \frac{\mu}{S} - \frac{q\gamma_1 I}{C} + \frac{\beta(\gamma_2 + \mu + \alpha q \gamma_1)(Ma_1 + Mb_1 + 1)}{\gamma_2 + \mu} I + Q(S, I, C) \\ &\leq -\frac{\mu}{\varepsilon} + U. \end{aligned} \quad (3.11)$$

where

$$U = \sup_{(S, I, C) \in R_+^3} \left\{ \frac{\beta(\gamma_2 + \mu + \alpha q \gamma_1)(Ma_1 + Mb_1 + 1)}{\gamma_2 + \mu} I + Q(S, I, C) \right\} < \infty. \quad (3.12)$$

It is easy for us to see that $LV(S, I, C) \leq -1$ for any given $(S, I, C) \in D_1$ by means of (3.5).

Case 2. If $(S, I, C) \in D_2$, then we get that

$$\begin{aligned}
LV &\leq -M\lambda - \frac{\mu}{S} + \frac{\beta(\gamma_2 + \mu + \alpha q\gamma_1)(Ma_1 + Mb_1 + 1)}{\gamma_2 + \mu} I + Q(S, I, C) \\
&\leq -M\lambda + \frac{\beta(\gamma_2 + \mu + \alpha q\gamma_1)(Ma_1 + Mb_1 + 1)}{\gamma_2 + \mu} I + F \\
&\leq -M\lambda + \frac{\beta(\gamma_2 + \mu + \alpha q\gamma_1)(Ma_1 + Mb_1 + 1)}{\gamma_2 + \mu} \varepsilon + F.
\end{aligned} \tag{3.13}$$

According to (3.6), the conclusion that $LV(S, I, C) \leq -1$ for any given $(S, I, C) \in D_2$ is true.

Case 3. If $(S, I, C) \in D_3$, then we see that

$$\begin{aligned}
LV &\leq -\frac{q\gamma_1 I}{C} + \frac{\beta(\gamma_2 + \mu + \alpha q\gamma_1)(Ma_1 + Mb_1 + 1)}{\gamma_2 + \mu} I + Q(S, I, C) \\
&\leq -\frac{q\gamma_1}{C} + U.
\end{aligned} \tag{3.14}$$

By means of (3.7), we obtain the conclusion that $LV(S, I, C) \leq -1$ for any given $(S, I, C) \in D_3$.

Case 4. If $(S, I, C) \in D_4$, then we attain that

$$\begin{aligned}
LV &\leq -\frac{1}{4}[\mu - \frac{\theta}{2}(\sigma_1^2 \vee \sigma_2^2 \vee \sigma_3^2)]S^{0+1} - \frac{1}{4}[\mu - \frac{\theta}{2}(\sigma_1^2 \vee \sigma_2^2 \vee \sigma_3^2)]S^{0+1} + \gamma_2 + 2\mu + \frac{\sigma_1^2 + \sigma_3^2}{2} \\
&\quad + \frac{\beta(\gamma_2 + \mu + \alpha q\gamma_1)(Ma_1 + Mb_1 + 1)}{\gamma_2 + \mu} I + B - \frac{1}{2}[\mu - \frac{\theta}{2}(\sigma_1^2 \vee \sigma_2^2 \vee \sigma_3^2)](I^{0+1} + C^{0+1}) \\
&\leq -\frac{1}{4}[\mu - \frac{\theta}{2}(\sigma_1^2 \vee \sigma_2^2 \vee \sigma_3^2)]S^{0+1} + G \\
&\leq -\frac{1}{4}[\mu - \frac{\theta}{2}(\sigma_1^2 \vee \sigma_2^2 \vee \sigma_3^2)]\frac{1}{\varepsilon^{0+1}} + G.
\end{aligned} \tag{3.15}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
D = \sup_{(S, I, C) \in \mathbb{R}_+^3} \{ &-\frac{1}{4}[\mu - \frac{\theta}{2}(\sigma_1^2 \vee \sigma_2^2 \vee \sigma_3^2)]S^{0+1} + \gamma_2 + 2\mu + \frac{\sigma_1^2 + \sigma_3^2}{2} \\
&+ \frac{\beta(\gamma_2 + \mu + \alpha q\gamma_1)(Ma_1 + Mb_1 + 1)}{\gamma_2 + \mu} I + B - \frac{1}{2}[\mu - \frac{\theta}{2}(\sigma_1^2 \vee \sigma_2^2 \vee \sigma_3^2)](I^{0+1} + C^{0+1}) \} < \infty.
\end{aligned} \tag{3.16}$$

It is obvious that $LV(S, I, C) \leq -1$ for any given $(S, I, C) \in D_4$ in virtue of (3.8).

Case 5. If $(S, I, C) \in D_5$, then we arrive at

$$\begin{aligned}
LV &\leq -\frac{1}{4}[\mu - \frac{\theta}{2}(\sigma_1^2 \vee \sigma_2^2 \vee \sigma_3^2)]I^{0+1} - \frac{1}{4}[\mu - \frac{\theta}{2}(\sigma_1^2 \vee \sigma_2^2 \vee \sigma_3^2)]I^{0+1} + \gamma_2 + 2\mu + \frac{\sigma_1^2 + \sigma_3^2}{2} \\
&\quad + \frac{\beta(\gamma_2 + \mu + \alpha q\gamma_1)(Ma_1 + Mb_1 + 1)}{\gamma_2 + \mu} I + B - \frac{1}{2}[\mu - \frac{\theta}{2}(\sigma_1^2 \vee \sigma_2^2 \vee \sigma_3^2)](S^{0+1} + C^{0+1}) \\
&\leq -\frac{1}{4}[\mu - \frac{\theta}{2}(\sigma_1^2 \vee \sigma_2^2 \vee \sigma_3^2)]I^{0+1} + H \\
&\leq -\frac{1}{4}[\mu - \frac{\theta}{2}(\sigma_1^2 \vee \sigma_2^2 \vee \sigma_3^2)]\frac{1}{\varepsilon^{0+1}} + H.
\end{aligned} \tag{3.17}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
H = \sup_{(S, I, C) \in \mathbb{R}_+^3} \{ &-\frac{1}{4}[\mu - \frac{\theta}{2}(\sigma_1^2 \vee \sigma_2^2 \vee \sigma_3^2)]I^{0+1} + \gamma_2 + 2\mu + \frac{\sigma_1^2 + \sigma_3^2}{2} \\
&+ \frac{\beta(\gamma_2 + \mu + \alpha q\gamma_1)(Ma_1 + Mb_1 + 1)}{\gamma_2 + \mu} I + B - \frac{1}{2}[\mu - \frac{\theta}{2}(\sigma_1^2 \vee \sigma_2^2 \vee \sigma_3^2)](S^{0+1} + C^{0+1}) \} < \infty.
\end{aligned} \tag{3.18}$$

With the aid of (3.9), the result that $LV(S, I, C) \leq -1$ for any given $(S, I, C) \in D_5$ is right.

Case 6. If $(S, I, C) \in D_6$, then we have a conclusion as follows

$$\begin{aligned}
 LV &\leq -\frac{1}{4}\left[\mu - \frac{\theta}{2}(\sigma_1^2 \vee \sigma_2^2 \vee \sigma_3^2)\right]C^{\theta+1} - \frac{1}{4}\left[\mu - \frac{\theta}{2}(\sigma_1^2 \vee \sigma_2^2 \vee \sigma_3^2)\right]C^{\theta+1} + \gamma_2 + 2\mu + \frac{\sigma_1^2 + \sigma_3^2}{2} \\
 &\quad + \frac{\beta(\gamma_2 + \mu + \alpha q \gamma_1)(Ma_1 + Mb_1 + 1)}{\gamma_2 + \mu} I + B - \frac{1}{2}\left[\mu - \frac{\theta}{2}(\sigma_1^2 \vee \sigma_2^2 \vee \sigma_3^2)\right](S^{\theta+1} + I^{\theta+1}) \\
 &\leq -\frac{1}{4}\left[\mu - \frac{\theta}{2}(\sigma_1^2 \vee \sigma_2^2 \vee \sigma_3^2)\right]C^{\theta+1} + N \\
 &\leq -\frac{1}{4}\left[\mu - \frac{\theta}{2}(\sigma_1^2 \vee \sigma_2^2 \vee \sigma_3^2)\right]\frac{1}{\varepsilon^{2(\theta+1)}} + N.
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.19}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
 N = \sup_{(S, I, C) \in R_+^3} \left\{ -\frac{1}{4}\left[\mu - \frac{\theta}{2}(\sigma_1^2 \vee \sigma_2^2 \vee \sigma_3^2)\right]C^{\theta+1} + \gamma_2 + 2\mu + \frac{\sigma_1^2 + \sigma_3^2}{2} \right. \\
 \left. + \frac{\beta(\gamma_2 + \mu + \alpha q \gamma_1)(Ma_1 + Mb_1 + 1)}{\gamma_2 + \mu} I + B - \frac{1}{2}\left[\mu - \frac{\theta}{2}(\sigma_1^2 \vee \sigma_2^2 \vee \sigma_3^2)\right](S^{\theta+1} + I^{\theta+1}) \right\} < \infty.
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.20}$$

We draw the conclusion that $LV(S, I, C) \leq -1$ for any given $(S, I, C) \in D_6$ by feat of (3.10).

From the discussion of a series of cases above, we come to a conclusion that

$$LV(S, I, C) \leq -1, (S, I, R) \in R_+^3 \setminus D_\varepsilon.$$

Next, the diffusion matrix of system (1.3) is

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_1^2 S^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_2^2 I^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \sigma_3^2 C^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

Let $c = \min_{(S, I, C) \in \bar{D}_k \subset R_+^3} \{\sigma_1^2 S^2, \sigma_2^2 I^2, \sigma_3^2 C^2\}$, then we can have

$$\sum_{i,j=1}^3 a_{ij}(x) \xi_i \xi_j = \sigma_1^2 S^2 \xi_1^2 + \sigma_2^2 I^2 \xi_2^2 + \sigma_3^2 C^2 \xi_3^2 \geq c |\xi|^2, (S, I, C) \in \bar{D}_k, \xi \in R^3.$$

Hence the condition (H1) in Lemma 3.1 is verified successfully.

As a result, according to Lemma 3.1, we get that there exists a unique ergodic stationary distribution. The proof is finished.

4 The extinction and persistence of system (1.3)

For convenience, we introduce the following notation and lemma.

$$\langle f(t) \rangle = \frac{1}{t} \int_0^t f(\zeta) d\zeta, \text{ herein } f(t) \text{ is an integral function on } [0, +\infty).$$

Lemma 4.1(Strong law of large number)(see [23]). Let $M = \{M_t\}_{t \geq 0}$ be a real valued continuous local martingale which disappear at $t = 0$. Then

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \langle M, M \rangle_t = \infty \text{ a.s.} \Rightarrow \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{M_t}{\langle M, M \rangle_t} = 0 \text{ a.s.}$$

also

$$\limsup_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\langle M, M \rangle_t}{t} < \infty \text{ a.s.} \Rightarrow \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{M_t}{t} = 0 \text{ a.s.}$$

Lemma 4.2 Assume that $(S(t), I(t), C(t))$ be the solution of the system (1.3) having the initial value $(S(0), I(0), C(0)) \in R_+^3$, then we get

$$\limsup_{t \rightarrow \infty} (S(t) + I(t) + C(t)) < \infty \text{ a.s.}$$

as well as

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{S(t)}{t} = 0, \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{I(t)}{t} = 0, \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{C(t)}{t} = 0, \text{ a.s.} \tag{4.1}$$

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\ln S(t)}{t} = 0, \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\ln I(t)}{t} = 0, \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\ln C(t)}{t} = 0, \text{ a.s.} \quad (4.2)$$

and

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\int_0^t S(\zeta) dB_1(\zeta)}{t} = 0, \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\int_0^t I(\zeta) dB_2(\zeta)}{t} = 0, \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\int_0^t C(\zeta) dB_3(\zeta)}{t} = 0. \text{ a.s.} \quad (4.3)$$

Proof. We have the following equation via the system (1.3)

$$d(S + I + C) = [\mu - \mu(S + I + C) - (1 - q)\gamma_1 I - \gamma_2 C] dt + \sigma_1 S dB_1(t) + \sigma_2 I dB_2(t) + \sigma_3 C dB_3(t). \quad (4.4)$$

By solving equation (4.4), we can get

$$\begin{aligned} S(t) + I(t) + C(t) &= 1 + (S(0) + I(0) + C(0) - 1)e^{-\mu t} - (1 - q)\gamma_1 \int_0^t e^{-\mu(t-\zeta)} I(\zeta) d(\zeta) \\ &\quad - \gamma_2 \int_0^t e^{-\mu(t-\zeta)} C(\zeta) d(\zeta) + \sigma_1 \int_0^t e^{-\mu(t-\zeta)} S(\zeta) B_1(\zeta) \\ &\quad + \sigma_2 \int_0^t e^{-\mu(t-\zeta)} I(\zeta) B_2(\zeta) + \sigma_3 \int_0^t e^{-\mu(t-\zeta)} C(\zeta) B_3(\zeta) \\ &\leq 1 + (S(0) + I(0) + C(0) - 1)e^{-\mu t} + N(t). \text{ a.s.} \end{aligned} \quad (4.5)$$

where

$$N(t) = \sigma_1 \int_0^t e^{-\mu(t-\zeta)} S(\zeta) dB_1(\zeta) + \sigma_2 \int_0^t e^{-\mu(t-\zeta)} I(\zeta) dB_2(\zeta) + \sigma_3 \int_0^t e^{-\mu(t-\zeta)} C(\zeta) dB_3(\zeta).$$

It is apparent that $N(t)$ is a continuous local martingale having the property of $N(0) = 0$.

Let

$$X(t) = X(0) + W(t) - P(t) + N(t).$$

at which

$$X(0) = S(0) + I(0) + C(0), W(t) = 1 - e^{-\mu t}, P(t) = [S(0) + I(0) + C(0)](1 - e^{-\mu t}).$$

By means of (4.5), we can get that

$$S(t) + I(t) + C(t) \leq X(t) \text{ a.s. } t \geq 0.$$

From the expression of $W(t)$ and $P(t)$, it is easy for us to see that $W(t)$ and $P(t)$ are continuous increasing course processing the property of $W(0) = P(0) = 0$ for all $t \geq 0$. So we can attain that $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} X(t) < \infty$

a.s. According to Theorem 3.9 in the literature [24]. Therefore

$$\limsup_{t \rightarrow \infty} (S(t) + I(t) + C(t)) < \infty \text{ a.s.}$$

Let

$$N_1(t) = \int_0^t S(\zeta) d(\zeta), N_2(t) = \int_0^t I(\zeta) d(\zeta), N_3(t) = \int_0^t C(\zeta) d(\zeta).$$

Then we can obtain

$$\limsup_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\langle N_1, N_1 \rangle_t}{t} \leq \sup_{t \geq 0} S^2(t) < \infty.$$

So according to Lemma 4.1, we have $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\int_0^t S(\zeta) dB_1(\zeta)}{t} = 0$. a.s. In a similar way, we can attain

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\int_0^t I(\zeta) dB_2(\zeta)}{t} = 0, \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\int_0^t C(\zeta) dB_3(\zeta)}{t} = 0. \text{ a.s.}$$

Next because $S(t), I(t), C(t)$ are bounded and positive, we have the conclusion

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{S(t)}{t} = 0, \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{I(t)}{t} = 0, \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{C(t)}{t} = 0, \text{ a.s.}$$

and

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\ln S(t)}{t} = 0, \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\ln I(t)}{t} = 0, \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\ln C(t)}{t} = 0, \text{ a.s.}$$

This finishes the proof of Lemma 4.2.

4.1 Extinction

In this subsection, we derive in detail the condition for the extinction of the disease.

Theorem 4.1 Assume that $(S(t), I(t), C(t))$ is the solution of the system (1.3) having the initial value $(S(0), I(0), C(0)) \in R_+^3$. If

$$\bar{R}_0 = \frac{6\beta(\gamma_1 + \mu)(\gamma_1 + \mu + \alpha q\gamma_1)}{(\gamma_1 + \mu)^2(\gamma_2 + \mu + \frac{\sigma_3^2}{2}) \wedge \frac{\sigma_2^2 q^2 \gamma_1^2}{2}} < 1,$$

then

$$\limsup_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\ln[q\gamma_1 I + (\gamma_1 + \mu)C]}{t} \leq \frac{(\gamma_1 + \mu)^2(\gamma_2 + \mu + \frac{\sigma_3^2}{2}) \wedge \frac{\sigma_2^2 q^2 \gamma_1^2}{2}}{2(\gamma_1 + \mu)^2} (\bar{R}_0 - 1) < 0.$$

as well as

$$\limsup_{t \rightarrow \infty} \langle S(t) \rangle = 1. \text{ a.s.}$$

Proof. Let $V_0(t) = \ln[q\gamma_1 I(t) + (\gamma_1 + \mu)C(t)]$, applying the Itô formula to $V_0(t)$, then we have

$$\begin{aligned} dV_0(t) &= \left\{ \frac{q\gamma_1 \beta SI + q\gamma_1 \alpha \beta SC - (\gamma_1 + \mu)(\gamma_2 + \mu)C}{q\gamma_1 I + (\gamma_1 + \mu)C} - \frac{q^2 \gamma_1^2 \sigma_2^2 I^2 + (\gamma_1 + \mu)^2 \sigma_3^2 C^2}{2[q\gamma_1 I + (\gamma_1 + \mu)C]^2} \right\} dt \\ &\quad + \frac{\sigma_2 q \gamma_1 I}{q\gamma_1 I + (\gamma_1 + \mu)C} dB_2(t) + \frac{\sigma_3 (\gamma_1 + \mu)C}{q\gamma_1 I + (\gamma_1 + \mu)C} dB_3(t) \\ &\leq \frac{\beta(\gamma_1 + \mu + \alpha q\gamma_1)S}{\gamma_1 + \mu} dt - \left[\frac{(\gamma_1 + \mu)(\gamma_2 + \mu)C}{q\gamma_1 I + (\gamma_1 + \mu)C} + \frac{q^2 \gamma_1^2 \sigma_2^2 I^2 + (\gamma_1 + \mu)^2 \sigma_3^2 C^2}{2[q\gamma_1 I + (\gamma_1 + \mu)C]^2} \right] dt \\ &\quad + \frac{\sigma_2 q \gamma_1 I}{q\gamma_1 I + (\gamma_1 + \mu)C} dB_2(t) + \frac{\sigma_3 (\gamma_1 + \mu)C}{q\gamma_1 I + (\gamma_1 + \mu)C} dB_3(t) \\ &\leq \frac{\beta(\gamma_1 + \mu + \alpha q\gamma_1)S}{\gamma_1 + \mu} dt - \frac{[(\gamma_1 + \mu)^2(\gamma_2 + \mu + \frac{\sigma_3^2}{2}) \wedge \frac{\sigma_2^2 q^2 \gamma_1^2}{2}](I^2 + C^2)}{[q\gamma_1 I + (\gamma_1 + \mu)C]^2} dt \\ &\quad + \frac{\sigma_2 q \gamma_1 I}{q\gamma_1 I + (\gamma_1 + \mu)C} dB_2(t) + \frac{\sigma_3 (\gamma_1 + \mu)C}{q\gamma_1 I + (\gamma_1 + \mu)C} dB_3(t) \\ &\leq \frac{\beta(\gamma_1 + \mu + \alpha q\gamma_1)S}{\gamma_1 + \mu} dt - \frac{1}{2(\gamma_1 + \mu)^2} [(\gamma_1 + \mu)^2(\gamma_2 + \mu + \frac{\sigma_3^2}{2}) \wedge \frac{\sigma_2^2 q^2 \gamma_1^2}{2}] dt \\ &\quad + \frac{\sigma_2 q \gamma_1 I}{q\gamma_1 I + (\gamma_1 + \mu)C} dB_2(t) + \frac{\sigma_3 (\gamma_1 + \mu)C}{q\gamma_1 I + (\gamma_1 + \mu)C} dB_3(t) \end{aligned} \quad (4.6)$$

In addition, according to the system (1.3), we can get

$$\begin{aligned} d(S + I + C) &= [\mu - \mu(S + I + C) - (\gamma_1 - q\gamma_1)I - \gamma_2 C] dt \\ &\quad + \sigma_1 S dB_1(t) + \sigma_2 I dB_2(t) + \sigma_3 C dB_3(t) \\ &\leq [\mu - \mu(S + I + C)] dt + \sigma_1 S dB_1(t) + \sigma_2 I dB_2(t) + \sigma_3 C dB_3(t). \end{aligned} \quad (4.7)$$

Integrating both sides of (4.7) from 0 to t and dividing by t , then taking the limit superior both sides of (4.7), finally by means of (4.3) in Lemma 4.2, we can obtain

$$\limsup_{t \rightarrow \infty} \langle S(t) + I(t) + C(t) \rangle \leq 1. \text{ a.s.}$$

Therefore from the inequation, we have the conclusion that

$$\limsup_{t \rightarrow \infty} \langle S(t) \rangle \leq 3. \text{ a.s.} \quad (4.8)$$

Integrating both sides of (4.6) from 0 to t and dividing by t , then taking the limit superior both sides of (4.6).

Further according to (4.8) and the assumption $\bar{R}_0 < 1$, we have the conclusion

$$\begin{aligned}
& \limsup_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\ln[q\gamma_1 I + (\gamma_1 + \mu)C]}{t} \\
& \leq \frac{3\beta(\gamma_1 + \mu + \alpha q\gamma_1)}{\gamma_1 + \mu} - \frac{1}{2(\gamma_1 + \mu)^2} [(\gamma_1 + \mu)^2(\gamma_2 + \mu + \frac{\sigma_3^2}{2}) \wedge \frac{\sigma_2^2 q^2 \gamma_1^2}{2}] \\
& = \frac{(\gamma_1 + \mu)^2(\gamma_2 + \mu + \frac{\sigma_3^2}{2}) \wedge \frac{\sigma_2^2 q^2 \gamma_1^2}{2}}{2(\gamma_1 + \mu)^2} (\bar{R}_0 - 1) < 0.
\end{aligned} \tag{4.9}$$

From (4.9), it is obvious that

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} I(t) = 0, \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} C(t) = 0. \text{ a.s. (4.10)}$$

Next, we take the integration of both sides of the system (1.3), then we obtain the following result

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{S(t) - S(0)}{t} &= \mu - \beta \langle S(t)I(t) \rangle - \alpha\beta \langle S(t)C(t) \rangle - \mu \langle S(t) \rangle + \sigma_1 \frac{\int_0^t S(\zeta) dB_1(\zeta)}{t} \\
\frac{I(t) - I(0)}{t} &= \beta \langle S(t)I(t) \rangle + \alpha\beta \langle S(t)C(t) \rangle - (\gamma_1 + \mu) \langle I(t) \rangle + \sigma_2 \frac{\int_0^t I(\zeta) dB_2(\zeta)}{t} \\
\frac{C(t) - C(0)}{t} &= q\gamma_1 \langle I(t) \rangle - (\gamma_2 + \mu) \langle C(t) \rangle + \sigma_3 \frac{\int_0^t C(\zeta) dB_3(\zeta)}{t}.
\end{aligned} \tag{4.11}$$

Adding up the three equality of (4.11), which yields

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{S(t) - S(0)}{t} + \frac{I(t) - I(0)}{t} + \frac{C(t) - C(0)}{t} &= \mu - \mu \langle S(t) \rangle - (\gamma_1 + \mu - q\gamma_1) \langle I(t) \rangle - (\gamma_2 + \mu) \langle C(t) \rangle \\
& \quad + \sigma_1 \frac{\int_0^t S(\zeta) dB_1(\zeta)}{t} + \sigma_2 \frac{\int_0^t I(\zeta) dB_2(\zeta)}{t} + \sigma_3 \frac{\int_0^t C(\zeta) dB_3(\zeta)}{t}.
\end{aligned} \tag{4.12}$$

By (4.1),(4.3),(4.10),(4.12), we draw the conclusion as follows

$$\limsup_{t \rightarrow \infty} \langle S(t) \rangle = 1. \text{ a.s.}$$

The proof is finished.

4.2 Persistence in mean

In this subsection, we will derive the condition for the persistence in mean of disease, at first, we introduce the definition of persistence in mean.

Definition 4.2 The system (1.3) is defined as persistence in mean if $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{t} \int_0^t I(\zeta) d\zeta > 0$. a.s.

Theorem 4.2 For given initial value $(S(0), I(0), C(0)) \in \Gamma$, if

$$R_0^S := \frac{\beta\mu}{(\mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_1^2)(\gamma_1 + \mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_2^2)} + \frac{\alpha\beta q\gamma_1\mu}{(\mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_1^2)(\gamma_1 + \mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_2^2)(\gamma_2 + \mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_3^2)} > 1,$$

then

$$\liminf_{t \rightarrow \infty} \langle I(t) \rangle \geq \frac{(\gamma_2 + \mu)(\gamma_1 + \mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_2^2)(R_0^S - 1)}{\beta(a_1 + b_1)(\gamma_2 + \mu + \alpha q\gamma_1)}. \text{ a.s.}$$

where

$$a_1 = \frac{\beta\mu}{(\mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_1^2)^2}, b_1 = \frac{\alpha\beta q\gamma_1\mu}{(\mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_1^2)^2(\gamma_2 + \mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_3^2)}.$$

In other words, the disease will prevail if $R_0^S > 1$.

Proof. Taking advantage of the same function as the proof of Theorem 3.1, let

$$V_1(S, I, C) = -\ln I - (a_1 + b_1) \ln S - b_2 \ln C + \frac{\alpha\beta(a_1 + b_1)}{\gamma_2 + \mu} C.$$

where a_1, b_1, b_2 are the same expression as the proof of Theorem 3.1. Using the Itô formula to V_1 , we can attain that

$$dV_1 = LV_1 dt - \sigma_2 dB_2(t) - (a_1 + b_1)\sigma_1 dB_1(t) - b_2\sigma_3 dB_3(t) + \frac{\alpha\beta(a_1 + b_1)}{\gamma_2 + \mu} \sigma_3 C dB_3(t). \quad (4.13)$$

From the proof of Theorem 3.1, we can get

$$\begin{aligned} LV &\leq -\frac{\beta\mu}{\mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_1^2} - \frac{\alpha\beta q\gamma_1\mu}{(\mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_1^2)(\gamma_2 + \mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_3^2)} + \gamma_1 + \mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_2^2 + \frac{\beta(a_1 + b_1)(\gamma_2 + \mu + \alpha q\gamma_1)}{\gamma_2 + \mu} I \\ &= -(\gamma_1 + \mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_2^2)(R_0^S - 1) + \frac{\beta(a_1 + b_1)(\gamma_2 + \mu + \alpha q\gamma_1)}{\gamma_2 + \mu} I. \end{aligned} \quad (4.14)$$

Next, based on (4.14), we take the integration both sides of (4.13) from 0 to t and dividing by t , then we can attain

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{V_1(S(t), I(t), C(t)) - V_1(S(0), I(0), C(0))}{t} &\leq -(\gamma_1 + \mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_2^2)(R_0^S - 1) \\ &\quad + \frac{\beta(a_1 + b_1)(\gamma_2 + \mu + \alpha q\gamma_1)}{\gamma_2 + \mu} \langle I(t) \rangle - \frac{\phi(t)}{t}. \end{aligned} \quad (4.15)$$

where

$$\phi(t) = \sigma_2 dB_2(t) + (a_1 + b_1)\sigma_1 dB_1(t) + b_2\sigma_3 dB_3(t) - \frac{\alpha\beta(a_1 + b_1)}{\gamma_2 + \mu} \sigma_3 C dB_3(t).$$

According Lemma 4.1 and (4.2) in Lemma 4.2, we can see that

$$\limsup_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\phi(t)}{t} = 0 \text{ a.s.}$$

Next using (4.2), (4.15) and taking advantage of the assumption that $R_0^S > 1$. Then by taking the limit inferior of both side of (4.15), we have

$$\liminf_{t \rightarrow \infty} \langle I(t) \rangle \geq \frac{(\gamma_2 + \mu)(\gamma_1 + \mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_2^2)(R_0^S - 1)}{\beta(a_1 + b_1)(\gamma_2 + \mu + \alpha q\gamma_1)}.$$

The proof is completed.

5 Numerical simulations

In this section, we will proceed in a numerical simulation to justify the theoretical results obtained in this paper.

Example 5.1. We choose the parameters as follows

$$q = 0.6, \beta = 0.01, \alpha = 0.1, \gamma_1 = 0.4, \gamma_2 = 0.01, \mu = 0.1.$$

and

$$\frac{\sigma_1^2}{2} = 0.025, \frac{\sigma_2^2}{2} = 0.3, \frac{\sigma_3^2}{2} = 0.1.$$

where the value of parameters α are from the literature [5] and the rest of the parameters are assumption. In addition, we make a assume that the initial values of the system (1.3) are

$$S(0) = 1.8, I(0) = 0.3, C(0) = 0.1.$$

Under this circumstance, we can verify

$$\bar{R}_0 = \frac{6\beta(\gamma_1 + \mu)(\gamma_1 + \mu + \alpha q\gamma_1)}{(\gamma_1 + \mu)^2(\gamma_2 + \mu + \frac{\sigma_3^2}{2}) \wedge \frac{\sigma_2^2 q^2 \gamma_1^2}{2}} \approx 0.9097 < 1.$$

So, it can be infer from Theorem 4.1 that $I(t) \rightarrow 0$ exponentially a.s. (see Fig.1)

Example 5.2. We choose the parameters as follows

$$q = 0.2, \beta = 0.8, \alpha = 0.1, \gamma_1 = 0.01, \gamma_2 = 0.001, \mu = 0.4$$

and

$$\frac{\sigma_1^2}{2} = 0.02, \frac{\sigma_2^2}{2} = 0.02, \frac{\sigma_3^2}{2} = 0.02.$$

Where the value of parameters $q, \alpha, \gamma_1, \gamma_2$ are from the literature [5] and the rest of the parameters are assumption. In addition, we make a assume that the initial values of the system (1.3) are

$$S(0) = 0.946, I(0) = 0.01, C(0) = 0.$$

On this condition, we can verify

$$R_0^S := \frac{\beta\mu}{(\mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_1^2)(\gamma_1 + \mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_2^2)} + \frac{\alpha\beta q\gamma_1\mu}{(\mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_1^2)(\gamma_1 + \mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_2^2)(\gamma_2 + \mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_3^2)} \approx 1.7727 > 1.$$

So, it can be infer from Theorem 3.1 and Theorem 4.2 that there is a unique stationary distribution and the disease is persistent. (see Fig.2 and Fig.3).

Figure 1: 3.1. (3.1.2) (3.1.3). (a) $S(t)$; (b) $I(t)$; (c) $C(t)$;

Figure 2: Persistence in mean: stochastic and deterministic cases. (a) Sample paths of $S(t)$; (b) Sample paths of $I(t)$; (c) Sample paths of $C(t)$

Figure 3: Distributions of $S(t)$, $I(t)$, $C(t)$ (a) Distribution of $S(t)$; (b) Distribution of $I(t)$; (c) Distribution of $C(t)$

6 Conclusions

Here we choose to put into force the dynamical study of the stochastic SICR epidemic model. First of all, we illustrate that there is a unique global positive solution for system (1.3) with the initial value. After that, we derive the conditions of the existence of ergodic stationary distribution of system (1.3). Then we also obtain the conditions of the extinction and persistence of the system (1.3). At last, we carry out the numerical simulation in order to make our results become more convinced.

Moreover, we present some interesting questions deserve further study. In this paper, the conditions of the extinction and persistence of disease are obtained, however, the corresponding deterministic model has a threshold, Is there a threshold for a random model? On the other hand, more realistic but more complex systems, such as, the stochastic epidemic model with time delay, periodic coefficient, Control, telephone noise and so on. We leave these questions for our future research work.

Conflict of Interests

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this paper.

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